

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Spain: An Introduction

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The number of local governments (municipalities) in Spain has slightly increased (around 0.2 per cent) along the last 40 years, since the first municipal elections of the democratic period took place. There are currently 8,131 municipalities but the reform for municipal consolidation (amalgamation) is not a salient issue in the political agenda in Spain. Although various attempts have been made in recent decades to encourage municipal mergers, all of them have failed. This explains why this option is not at the top of the current political agenda. In this failure, the strong identity factor proper to the municipalities in Spain has played a salient role.

Figure 2: Municipalities in Spain.

More than 80 per cent of the 8,131 Spanish municipalities have a very small size in terms of population, counting less than 5,000 inhabitants. In terms of population, 61 per cent of all municipalities in Spain have less than 1,000 inhabitants who account for only just over 3 per cent of the entire population of the country. In front of them, those with between 10,000 and 100,000 inhabitants (8.5 per cent of the total) and those of more than 100,000 (0.75 per cent) concentrate 80 per cent of the entire Spanish population (40 per cent each group). Given the technical and economic limitations of the small municipalities to provide services

autonomously, they are replaced or supplemented by the 50 provinces, which present a remarkable financial capacity.

Figure 3: Provinces in Spain.

In this context, inter-municipal cooperation plays a crucial role in local governance. It is usually based on inter-municipal agreements, which are bilateral or multilateral, and often lead to the establishment of inter-municipal institutions and associations, such as the *mancomunidades* (commonwealths) directly created by the municipalities. Inter-municipal cooperation is used in all its forms to profit from economies of scale effects and to prevent centralization of competences. Most Spanish municipalities cooperate in the field of water supply and treatment of waste water, as well as in garbage collection and waste disposal and many others, especially those of small sizes, in other services such as social policies.

Spain is a country with a high degree of urbanization, but concentrated in a very small territory. Despite the evidence of the metropolitanization process, the Spanish political/legal system has not responded to this phenomenon. The creation of metropolitan areas' governments or formal coordination agreements is a responsibility of the autonomous communities that, in general, have decided not to promote their establishment. In fact, Catalonia as well as Galicia and Valencia show reluctance and ambiguity when facing the creation of strong metropolitan governments in, respectively, the cities of Barcelona, Vigo and Valencia.

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